

HYDRAULIC CONDUCTIVITY OF FINE-GRAINED SOILS STABILIZED WITH PLANTAIN PEEL POWDER AS PARTIAL REPLACEMENT FOR LIME

Segun J. AKINRIMISI^{1*}, Elijah O. AJAYI², Mayowa V. AGUNBIADE³, Salaudeen O. LATEEF⁴ and Olabisi A. FADAHUNSI⁴

¹Department of Civil Engineering, Olusegun Agagu University of Science and Technology, Okitipupa.

²Department of Civil Engineering, Redeemer University Ede, Osun State.

³Maguns Global Resources Ltd, Akure.

⁴Levant Construction Ltd, Abuja.

*Corresponding Author: sj.akinrimisi@oaustech.edu.ng

Abstract

This study investigates the effects of plantain peel powder (PPP) as a sustainable stabilizing agent on the geotechnical properties of two clayey soils obtained from Mandate Lodge (MC) and Ora-Ayoka (OAC) in Kwara State, Nigeria. Laboratory tests, conducted according to BS 1377:1990, evaluated the Atterberg limits, compaction characteristics, California Bearing Ratio (CBR), and hydraulic conductivity at PPP contents of 1–10% by weight of dry soil. The Mandate clay exhibited higher natural moisture content (19.22%) and specific gravity (2.78) compared to Ora-Ayoka clay (11.95% and 2.66). Both soils were well graded. The liquid and plastic limits decreased progressively with increasing PPP, indicating reduced plasticity and improved workability. Maximum dry density decreased while optimum moisture content increased, attributed to PPP's low specific gravity and filler nature. CBR values improved with moderate PPP inclusion, peaking at 4% for MC (64%) and 6% for OAC (36%), before declining due to excess organic matter. Hydraulic conductivity decreased with increasing PPP, signifying enhanced impermeability. Overall, plantain peel powder at 4–6% replacement effectively enhanced soil strength and reduced permeability, promoting sustainable reuse of agro-waste in geotechnical applications.

Keywords

Hydraulic Conductivity, Fine-Grained Soils, Soil Stabilization, Lime, Plantain Peel Powder.

1. INTRODUCTION

Soil stabilization refers to the process of improving the engineering properties of natural soils to make them more suitable for construction and environmental applications. The primary goal is to enhance soil strength, hydraulic conductivity, and durability against repeated wetting and drying, as well as to promote environmental sustainability [2]. Historically, geotechnical engineers were constrained to design foundations that merely adapted to the prevailing subsoil conditions at a given site. However, with advancements in geotechnical techniques and materials science, it is now possible to permanently modify weak soils to achieve desired engineering properties, regardless of their initial limitations.

Soil improvement techniques are generally categorized as mechanical, chemical, physical, or biological. Mechanical stabilization increases density and strength through compaction or blending with granular materials [15]. Chemical stabilization, which remains the most widely adopted, involves the addition of binders such as lime, cement, or fly ash that react with clay minerals to reduce plasticity and improve load-bearing capacity [25]. Recently, agricultural by-products—such as plantain peel ash, cassava peel ash, and palm kernel shell ash—have been explored as eco-friendly and sustainable alternatives to traditional stabilizers [11]. Grouting techniques, involving the injection of cementitious or chemical materials, are also used to fill soil voids and increase cohesion in foundations and tunneling operations [7]. The inclusion of geosynthetics, such as geotextiles and geogrids, provides reinforcement and helps control settlement and lateral deformation [8, 2]. Dewatering techniques like vertical drains improve consolidation in soft soils [6], while biological approaches—especially Microbial-Induced Calcite Precipitation (MICP)—offer environmentally friendly alternatives by binding soil particles through

biogenic calcium carbonate precipitation [5]. The choice of stabilization method depends on soil type, environmental constraints, and project requirements [3].

Fine-grained soils composed predominantly of clay and silt particles smaller than 0.075 mm, exhibit high plasticity, low permeability, and significant water retention capacity. Their engineering behavior is largely governed by mineralogy and moisture content: when saturated, they soften and lose shear strength; when desiccated, they shrink and crack. Clay minerals such as kaolinite, illite, and montmorillonite greatly influence these properties [3]. Due to their tendency to swell, shrink, and consolidate, fine-grained soils often require stabilization before use in foundations, embankments, or pavements. Their classification and performance are typically evaluated through Atterberg limits, grain size distribution, and compaction tests [6].

Plantain peel powder (PPP), a by-product of *Musa paradisiaca*, has emerged as a promising bio-based stabilizer. PPP is prepared by washing, drying (at 60–80°C), pulverizing, and sieving the peels to fine powder [13]. Chemically, it contains cellulose, hemicellulose, lignin, and reactive oxides such as silica, alumina, calcium, magnesium, and potassium [15]. When calcined, PPP exhibits pozzolanic reactivity, allowing it to form cementitious compounds such as calcium silicate hydrate (C–S–H) and calcium aluminate hydrate (C–A–H) in the presence of lime, which enhance soil strength and reduce permeability [18]. Prior studies [16] report improvements in unconfined compressive strength, reductions in plasticity, and enhanced durability in fine-grained soils stabilized with PPP. As a biodegradable and renewable material, PPP represents a sustainable alternative to synthetic stabilizers, contributing to circular-economy practices in geotechnical engineering.

Although several studies have evaluated agricultural waste ashes for soil stabilization (e.g., cassava peel, palm kernel shell, and banana/plantain residues), the role of finely ground plantain peel powder (PPP) as a partial replacement for lime has not been sufficiently quantified with respect to hydraulic conductivity. Most prior works emphasize strength and consistency limits, leaving the permeability response—and its relationship with compaction and strength—underexplored for fine grained Nigerian soils. This study addresses this gap by evaluating how PPP (0–10% by dry soil) modifies Atterberg limits, compaction parameters (MDD, OMC), California Bearing Ratio (CBR), and hydraulic conductivity of two representative clays from Kwara State. The objective is to identify an optimum PPP content that balances strength improvement and permeability reduction in line with relevant standards.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Collection and Identification of Sample

For the purpose of this research, the materials needed which are fine-grained soil (clay) and plantain peel powder were sourced from Omu-Aran. Omu-Aran is a town in Irepodun local government area of Kwara state. Two different samples were obtained from the two locations. Two fine-grained soils were sampled from Mandate Lodge (MC) and Ora-Ayoka (OAC) in Omu-Aran, Irepodun LGA, Kwara State, Nigeria. Plantain peels were sourced locally.

Plantain peels were washed to remove adhering impurities, oven dried at 80 °C for 24 h, pulverized using a mechanical grinder, and sieved through a 75 µm sieve to obtain PPP. PPP was blended with soil at 0, 2, 4, 6, 8, and 10% by dry mass of soil. Blends were homogenized; moisture conditioned to target OMC during compaction, sealed, and cured for 7 days prior to CBR and permeability tests unless.

Figure 2.1: Plantain peel and plantain peel powder used for the research

2.2. Preliminary Tests

i Natural Moisture Content (NMC)

Natural moisture content is the amount of water present in pore space between the soil grains which is removed by oven drying at a specific temperature. The method is based on removing soil moisture by oven-drying a soil sample until the weight remains constant. The equipment used is: weighing balance, a metal container, a drying oven at temperature 105-115°C. The moisture content (%) is calculated from the sample weight before and after drying. A clean, dry container was weighed to the nearest gram. A container with sample was measure w_2 . Then it was placed in a drying oven for 24 hr. After, the oven drying sample were measure with container as w_3 .

ii Specific Gravity (SG)

The term specific gravity of soil actually refers to the specific gravity of the solid matter of the soil which is designated G, the specific gravity of solid is normally only applied to that fraction of the soil that pass through No. 4 sieve. Generally, geotechnical engineers need the specific gravity of soil samples to perform further test. A soil's specific gravity largely depends on the density of the material making the individual soil particles. Some of the apparatus needed are thermometer, pudding pan, heat-resistant gloves, a laboratory oven etc.

iii Liquid Limit (LL)

Soil of at least 200g that passed through sieve number 40, placed on a glass plate then mixed with distilled water into a paste. A groove is then cut at the centre of the soil paste, with standard grooving tool. By the use of the cranked-operated cam, the cup is lifted and dropped, the moisture content, in percentage, required to close the distance along the bottom of the groove after 25 blows is determined according to BS 1377 (1990).

iv Plastic Limit (PL)

200g of soils that pass-through sieve number 40 was prepared in liquid limit, the soil was mixed with water to make it sufficiently plastic for rolling into a ball, which was then rolled out between the hand and glass plate to form a thread. The soil was said to be at its plastic limit when it begins to crumble at a thread diameter of 3mm. At this stage it is removed for moisture content determination. Natural moisture content and specific gravity: The determination of specific gravity, and natural moisture content tests will follow the standard as outlined in BS 1377 of 1990.

v Plasticity Index

$$\text{Plasticity, } PI = \text{Liquid Limit, } LL - \text{Plastic Limit, } PL \quad (1)$$

vi Sieve Analysis

The pulverized sample was washed to remove all clayey materials finer than the 0.075mm diameter and oven dried. The oven dried sample was poured into the stack of sieves from the top and sieved in a shaker manually. The test was done in accordance to ASTM D422.

2.3. Major/Detailed Test

i Hydraulic Conductivity (K)

This is symbolically represented by K. it is a property of a vascular soil that describes the ease with which a fluid (usually water) can move through the pore space or fracture. It depends on the intrinsic permeability of the material, the degree of saturation, and the density and viscosity of the fluid.

The falling head permeability test is a common laboratory testing method used to determine the permeability of fine-grained soils with intermediate and low permeability such as silts and clays. This testing method can be applied to disturbed and undisturbed soil sample. In order to investigate the effect of adding plantain peel to soil permeability, a series of laboratory permeability tests on non-stabilized and stabilized soils was conducted according to BS1377: Part 5:1990.

The steps used for test are as follows:

1. Permeameter cell was filled with soil compacted at optimum moisture content and maximum dry density in three layers.
2. Filter paper was placed on both sides of permeameter cell and porous stone on bottom of permeameter cell.
3. Manometer tubes were connected, but valves kept closed.
4. Air was removed from soil sample for 15 minutes through inlet tube located at top of permeameter cell.
5. Test was run and readings taken i.e., h_1 and h_2 , and time taken to reach h_2

ii **Compaction**

The Modified Proctor compaction test was carried out to determine the moisture content-dry density relationship according to BS1377: Part 4:1990. Soil sample was treated with plantain peel at different percentage such as 2 %, 4 %, 6%,8 %, and 10 % in order to investigate the effect of adding plantain peel on optimum water content and maximum dry density of the selected soils. The soil was compacted into 9.56 x 10-4m²moulds in 5 equal layers with each layer given twenty-five blows. The blows were evenly distributed over the surface of the layer. The collar of the mould was then removed and the compacted sample weighed. The procedure was repeated until the weight of compacted sample was noted to be decreasing. The optimum moisture content (OMC) and maximum dry density (MDD) were determined.

iii **California Bearing Ratio**

California Bearing Ratio (CBR) is defined as the ratio of the force per unit area required to penetrate a soil mass with a circular plunger of 50 mm diameter at the rate of 1.25 mm/min to that required for corresponding penetration of a standard material. The ratio is usually determined for penetrations of 2.5 and 5 mm. Where the ratio at 5 mm is consistently higher than that as 2.5 mm, the ratio at 5 mm is used.

For the requirements of pavement design, one of the simple strength tests would be a plate bearing test on the sub grade using the plate area and loading approximately equal to the anticipated contact area and the wheel load. Field tests require heavy equipment and considerable time. The California Bearing Ratio method provides a good substitute for heavy field tests. Thus, it is the simple test, internationally accepted for design of flexible pavements. For such pavements, it is considered to be the most reliable method available, provided these tests are carried out under the specified condition. These were done in accordance with ASTM D4429 - 09a using the CBR machine.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The interpretation of results obtained from work done on the effect of varying percentages of plantain peels on the Atterberg limits, hydraulic conductivity, compaction and California bearing ratio of the soil under investigation has been explained below.

3.1 Results of Preliminary Test

3.1.1 Natural Moisture Content: The natural moisture content of the soil from the two locations is as presented in Tables 3.1 and 3.2. It can be noticed that Mandate has an average of 19.22% which is higher than that of Ora-Ayoka that is 11.95 %. This shows that Mandate Clay has higher water retaining capacity than the other one.

Table 3.1: Natural Moisture Content for Mandate Clay

Samples ID	Weight of Empty Can (g) A	Weight of Wet Sample (g) B	Weight of Oven-Dried Sample (g) C	MC (%) = (B-C/C-A) *100
A	22	42.5	39	20.59
B	23	44	40.5	20.00
C	22.5	46.5	43	17.07
AVERAGE				19.22

Table 3.2: Natural Moisture Content for Ora-Ayoka Clay

Samples ID	Weight of Empty Can (g) A	Weight of Wet Sample (g) B	Weight of Oven-Dried Sample (g) C	MC (%) = (B-C/C-A) *100
A	19.5	42	39.5	12.50
B	22	43.5	41	13.16
C	21	48	45.5	10.20
Average				11.95

3.1.2 Specific Gravity

Specific gravity test is the ratio of the weight in air of a given volume of soil at a standard temperature to the weight in air of an equal volume of distilled water at the same stated temperature. Table 3.3 and 3.4 show the data obtained from the specific gravity test conducted on the samples from both locations, the result obtained was 2.78 and 2.66 respectively. Generally, the specific gravity of clay is between 2.60 – 2.80.

Table 3.3. Specific Gravity for Mandate Clay

Sample ID	A	B	C
Mass of Bottle + sample +Water (M3)	78.5	80.5	81
Mass of Bottle + sample (M2)	30	32.5	33.5
Mass of Bottle Full of Water Only (M4)	70	70	70
Mass of Bottle (M1)	16	16	16
Mass of Water Used (M3-M2)	48.5	48	47.5
Mass Of sample Used (M2-M1)	14	16.5	17.5
Volume Of sample (M4-M1) -(M3-M2)	5.5	6	6.5
$G_s=(M2-M1)/(M4-M1) -(M3-M2)$	2.55	2.75	2.69
AVERAGE GS		2.66	

Figures 3.1 and 3.2 show the graphs representing the results of the sieve analysis test performed on both samples. From the graph, it can be deduced that the samples are well graded, that is, D10, D30, and D60 (which are, correspondingly, the diameters corresponding to percentage finer of 10%, 30%, and 60%) were obtained to be 0.06 mm, 0.075 mm and 0.182 mm and 0.08mm, 0.15 mm and 0.285 mm respectively so as to determine parameters such as the effective size (D10), the Uniformity Coefficient, CU and Coefficient of Gradation, Cc.

Table 3.4. Specific Gravity for Ora-Ayoka Clay

Sample ID	A	B	C
Mass of Bottle + sample +Water (M3)	81	79.5	80.5
Mass of Bottle + sample (M2)	33.5	31	32
Mass of Bottle Full of Water Only (M4)	70	70	70
Mass of Bottle (M1)	16	16	16
Mass of Water Used (M3-M2)	47.5	48.5	48.5
Mass Of sample Used (M2-M1)	17.5	15	16
Volume Of sample (M4-M1) -(M3-M2)	6.5	5.5	5.5
$G_s=(M2-M1)/(M4-M1) -(M3-M2)$	2.69	2.73	2.91
AVERAGE GS		2.78	

- i Effective Size = D10 = 0.06 and 0.08 mm respectively
- ii Uniformity Coefficient, Cu = D60/D10= 3.0 and 4.0 respectively
- iii Coefficient of gradation, Cc = D30²/D60xD10= 0.5 and 1.0 respectively

Figure 3.1. Sieve Analysis for Mandate Clay

Figure 3.2. Sieve Analysis for Ora-Ayoka Clay

3.1.4 Atterberg Limits

The Atterberg limit results indicate that both Mandate Clay and Ora-Ayoka Clay are low-plasticity soils, with liquid limits of 30% and 31% respectively, classifying them as inorganic clays of low to medium plasticity (CL) under BS 5930 and ASTM D2487. The plasticity index of Mandate Clay (10.5%) is slightly higher than that of Ora-Ayoka Clay (7.5%), suggesting a marginally greater potential for volume change. However, both values fall within the low plasticity range, indicating moderate workability and minimal swelling behavior. Linear shrinkage values of 4.8% for Mandate and 6.2% for Ora-Ayoka fall below the 8% threshold, confirming low shrinkage potential per BS 1377-2. Overall, both soils are suitable for engineering use with minimal stabilization, though Mandate Clay may require slightly more attention in moisture-sensitive applications.

Table 3.5. Atterberg Limit for the two locations (MC and OAC)

S/N	PARAMETERS	MANDATE CLAY	ORA-AYOKA CLAY
1	Liquid Limit (%)	30	31
2	Plastic Limit (%)	19.5	23.5
3	Linear Shrinkage Limit (%)	4.8	6.2
4	Plasticity Index	10.5	7.5

3.2 Results of Major Tests before and after Stabilization

After mixing the plantain peels with the soil from the two locations, detailed test such as Atterberg limits, compaction, permeability and California bearing ratio were carried out and the results are presented in the sub-sections below.

3.2.1 Atterberg Limit

Figures 3.3 and 3.4 show the result obtained for liquid limit, plastic limit and plasticity index for both samples. This illustrates the effect of incorporating plantain peel (PP) into clay soil on its Atterberg limits specifically, the liquid limit (LL), plastic limit (PL), and plasticity index (PI). As the percentage of PP increases from 0% to 10%, both LL and PL consistently decrease, indicating a progressive reduction in the soil's moisture sensitivity and plasticity. This downward trend suggests that plantain peel reduces the amount of water required for the soil to transition between liquid and plastic states, thereby enhancing its dimensional stability. The plasticity index, which reflects the range of moisture content within which the soil remains plastic, also drops significantly from approximately 9% to 6%. According to ASTM D4318 and ASTM D2487 standards, this behavior signifies a transition toward low-plasticity soil, with reduced shrink-swell potential and improved workability. The consistent decrease in all three parameters confirms that plantain peel acts as a pozzolanic stabilizer, improving the geotechnical performance of clay by altering its consistency limits, making it more suitable for use in subgrade, pavement, and foundation engineering applications. These results are in line with the observations made by [14] in their research on Correlation of Soil Properties with *Costus cupreifolius* maas Admixture during Stabilization.

Figure 3.3: Atterberg Limit for location A (Mandate Lodge, Landmark)

Figure 3.4. Atterberg Limit for location B (Ora-Ayoka, Omu-Aran)

3.2.2 Compaction

Standard Proctor compaction test was carried out to determine the optimum moisture content and maximum dry density of the blended soil from the two locations. The test results are shown in Figure 3.5 (maximum dry density) and Figure 3.6 (optimum moisture content). The results show that the optimum moisture content increases while the maximum dry density of the plantain peels blended clay decreased with increasing replacement level. This is due to the fact that plantain peels are lighter compared to the clay soil. The observed decrease in MDD values can be attributed to mixture of the soil and plantain peels which have lower specific gravity compared to the soil. The observed decrease in MDD may also be explained by considering the plantain peels as filler in the soil voids [22]. Increase in OMC values implies that more water is needed to compact the soil [4, 19]

Figure 3.5. Maximum Dry Density for both Samples

Figure 3.6. Optimum Moisture Content for both Samples

3.2.3 California Bearing Ratio (CBR)

California Bearing Ratio is one of the common tests widely used in the design of base and subbase material for pavement design and it is used to evaluate the strength of stabilized soil [10] [19]. For the plantain peels, the CBR rose progressively at 0% value of 31 % to 64 % at 4% value. It reduced to 45 %, 36% and 32 % at 6%, 8 % and 10 % respectively for MC. A similar trend was observed for OAC, it increased gradually from 24 % at 0 % PP to 36 % at 6 % and later decrease to 23 % and 21 % at 8 % and 10 % respectively. Decrease in the CBR values may be due to the excess plantain peels which was not mobilized in the reaction as the presence of naturally occurring Calcium hydroxide in the soil may be small. The excess plantain peels occupy space within the specimen and reduces the clay and silt content in soil and hence, reduces the bond/cohesion in the soil- plantain peels [15]

According to [25] increase in values of CBR may be because of the gradual formation of cementitious compounds in the reaction between plantain peels and some amounts of Calcium hydroxide present in the soil. The optimum value for MC is therefore at 4% of weight of soil while that of OAC is 6 % weight of soil.

Figure 3.7. CBR for both Samples

3.2.4 Hydraulic Conductivity or Permeability

The variation of hydraulic conductivity is shown in Figure 3.8. Generally, the hydraulic conductivity decreased with increase in the percentage of plantain peels from 0 % to 10 % by weight of soil. This is due to the consistent increase in the optimum moisture content as earlier reported. This result is consistent with the results of [11]. The values obtained for the two locations were all higher than the maximum permissible hydraulic conductivity of 1×10^{-9} m/s. The optimum obtained for the two samples is at 10 % plantain peels, which simply suggest that any further increase can lead to achieving a value less than the permissible limit.

Figure 3.8. Hydraulic Conductivity for both Samples

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

4.1 Conclusion

- 1) PPP reduced liquid and plastic limits and narrowed plasticity indices for clays, signaling improved workability and lower shrink–swell potential.
- 2) PPP increased OMC and reduced MDD, consistent with its lower specific gravity and filler effect.
- 3) CBR peaked at 4% PPP for MC (64%) and 6% for OAC (36%), beyond which values declined.
- 4) Hydraulic conductivity decreased with PPP content up to 10%, indicating pore refinement and enhanced impermeability.

Overall, an optimal PPP range of 4–6% is recommended to balance strength and permeability improvements for fine-grained subgrades. For stringent cut-off applications, higher PPP may be explored with confirmatory strength/durability checks.

4.2 Recommendations for practice and future work

- Adopt 4–6% PPP (by dry soil) when targeting combined CBR and workability gains; verify with project-specific compaction and curing protocols.
- Where very low permeability is critical, investigate 8–10% PPP with microstructural characterization (SEM/EDS, XRD) and durability tests.
- Calibrate performance against national standards (e.g., Nigerian Federal Ministry of Works) including soaked/unsaturated CBR and durability cycles.
- Conduct life-cycle and cost analyses to quantify economic and environmental benefits of PPP as a lime-replacement strategy.

REFERENCES

- [1] Afeez A. B, Joseph .A., Ige and Hammed.A (2015). Stabilization of Lateritic Soil with Cassava Peels Ash. *British Journal of Applied Science & Technology*, 648.
- [2] Akinbuluma, A. T., Ogundare, D. A., & Alengaram, U. J. (2025). The use of pozzolanic materials for road stabilization in Africa: A review. *Materials Research Proceedings*, 51. <https://doi.org/10.21741/9781644903537-8>
- [3] Das, B. M., & Sobhan, K. (2018). *Principles of Geotechnical Engineering* (9th ed.). Cengage Learning.
- [4] Ogundare, D. A., Adeleke, O. O., & Akinbuluma, A. T. (2024). Chemical and Mechanical Characterisation of Clay Soil Stabilised with Steel Slag and Calcium Carbide Waste. *Civil and Sustainable Urban Engineering*, 4(1), 55-64.
- [5] DeJong, J. T., Mortensen, B. M., Martinez, B. C., & Nelson, D. C. (2010). Bio-mediated soil improvement. *Ecological Engineering*, 36(2), 197–210.
- [6] Holtz, R. D., Kovacs, W. D., & Sheahan, T. C. (2011). *An Introduction to Geotechnical Engineering* (2nd ed.). Pearson.
- [7] Karol, R. H. (2003). *Chemical Grouting and Soil Stabilization* (3rd ed.). CRC Press.
- [8] Koerner, R. M. (2012). *Designing with Geosynthetics* (6th ed.). Xlibris Corporation.
- [9] Little, D. N. (1995). *Handbook for Stabilization of Pavement Subgrades and Base Courses with Lime*. National Lime Association.
- [10] Theophilus, A. A., & Kennedy, C. (2023). Correlation of Soil Properties with *Costus cupreifolius* maas Admixture during Stabilization. *Saudi J Civ Eng*, 7(2), 9-15.
- [11] Osinubi, K. J., Eberemu, A. O., & Oyelakin, M. A. (2019). Sustainable soil stabilization using agricultural waste ash. *Transportation Geotechnics*, 21, (1) 00309. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trgeo.2019.100309>
- [12] Akinbuluma, A. T., Md Isa, M. H., & Ogundare, D. A. (2025). African lateritic soils and pavements failure: A review. *OAUSTECH Journal of Engineering and Intelligent Technology*, 1(1), 205–216. <https://doi.org/10.36108/ojeit/5202.10.0122>
- [13] Adewumi, J. A., Ajayi, A. O., & Ogunjimi, A. O. (2021). Production and characterization of plantain peel ash for potential use in soil stabilization. *Nigerian Journal of Technological Development*, 18(2), 45–51.
- [14] Theophilus, A. A., & Kennedy, C. (2023). Effectiveness of *Costus asplundii* maas as Admixture of Lime in Soil Stabilization of Highway Pavement. DOI: 10.36349/easjmb.2023.v06i02.001
- [15] Olutola, S. A., Odetoyan, O. O., & Fapohunda, C. A. (2022). Pozzolanic activity of plantain peel ash in partial cement replacement. *Heliyon*, 8(11), e11578. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e11578>
- [16] Umar, H. S., Mustapha, A. M., & Yusuf, A. (2023). Stabilization of clay soil using plantain peel ash as a bio-additive. *International Journal of Geotechnical Engineering*, 17(3), 243–254. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19386362.2022.2038119>
- [17] Akinbuluma, A. T., Omoniyi, A. G., & Seun, T. O. (2025). Intelligent transportation system for urban mobility: A review of route optimization algorithms and environmental data integration. *Advance Journal of Science, Engineering and Technology*, 10(5), 1–26.
- [18] Adekola, A. O., & Aladejare, A. E. (2021). Effect of calcined agricultural waste ashes on geotechnical properties of lateritic soils. *Case Studies in Construction Materials*, 15, e00699. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cscm.2021.e00699>
- [19] Chang, I., Im, J., Prasadhi, A. K., and Cho, G. C. (2015). “Effects of Xanthan gum biopolymer on soil strengthening.” *Construction and Building Materials*, 74, 65–72.
- [20] Osinubi, K.J., Ijimdiya, T.S. and Nmadu, I. (2009.) “Lime Stabilization of Black Cotton Soil using Bagasse Ash as Admixture,” *Advanced Materials Research*, 62-64, 3-10.
- [21] BS 1377. Methods of Testing Soil for Civil Engineering Purposes. *British Standards Institute, London; 1990*

- [22] Joel, M., & Agbede, I. O. (2010). Mechanical-cement stabilization of laterite for use as flexible pavement material. *Journal on Materials of Civil Engineering*, 10.1061/(ASCE)MT.1943-5533.0000148, 146–152.
- [23] BS 1924. Methods of Test for Stabilized Soils. *British Standards Institute, London;1990*.
- [24] BSI (British Standards Institution). (1990a). *British standard methods of test for soils for civil Engineering Purposes—Part 2: Classification tests*. BS1377, London.
- [25] Aderinola O. S. & Nnochiri, E. S. (2017). Stabilizing Lateritic Soil Using Terrasil Solution. *SSP Journal of Civil Engineering*, 12(1), 33-36
- [26] Koerner, R.M. (2012). *Designing with Geosynthetics*. 6th Edition, Xlibris Publishing Co., New York.
- [27] DeJong, J. T., Mortensen, B. M., Martinez, B. C., & Nelson, D. C. (2010). “Bio-Mediated Soil Improvement.” *Ecological Engineering*, 36, 197–210.
- [28] Braja M. Das & Khaled Sobhan (2018). *Principles of Geotechnical Engineering* (7th ed., Cengage Learning)